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ABSTRACT

The nonlinear dielectric properties of polyimide (PI) films, excited by high-intensity, AC electric fields, have been measured. This work highlights that nonlinear DC conduction is a component of the AC conductivity and dielectric loss response when surpassing a certain threshold field strength. An additional Poole–Frenkel polarization, induced by high-intensity, high-frequency fields, also contributes to the nonlinearity. This increases the dielectric losses through a charge de-trapping process, the so-called “jacking-up” effect. A novel expression that captures the large signal behavior of the complex permittivity is introduced using the Cole–Cole format. Finally, it is shown that the dielectric properties and power dissipation density in PI films remain fully linear and frequency-independent up to an AC electric field of $E_{PF} \sim 100 V_{rms}/\mu m$ and more conservatively below a threshold field of $E_X \sim 45 V/\mu m$ (i.e., end of the ohmic region). Consequently, polyimide-based insulated electronic devices that are designed to continuously operate below this threshold field (including both uniform and fringe fields) will remain immune to a frequency-dependent electrical aging. Their lifetime should not be affected in any way.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Insulating polymers and inorganic materials are used in high-voltage electronic devices, such as thin film capacitors, gate dielectrics, and digital isolators.^{1–5} In general, the current–field relationship exhibited by their constituent materials is not linear and can originate from many physical phenomena including non-parabolicity of potential wells, ionization, or space charge limiting. Understanding the nonlinear dielectric behavior of these materials, subjected to intense, high-frequency electric fields, is technologically important. Particularly significant is the threshold field value, E_{th} , typically in the range of tens of $V/\mu m$, above which the dielectric properties switch from being linear to nonlinear. Such values can be reached, for example, in a digital isolator where the fringe field values can be a factor five times greater than the bulk due to the high curvature of the micrometer size geometries. In the nonlinear regime, the electrical insulation performance deteriorates, displaying increased harmonic content and significantly enhanced dielectric losses.⁶ This is accompanied by accelerated electrical aging processes, such as dielectric heating, resulting in a shortened

operational lifetime for a device. Consequently, an accurate measurement of the threshold field, under which the electrical aging processes can be considered negligible,^{7,8} is essential for the design of reliable devices that operate at high voltage (<2 kV) and high frequency (>10 kHz).

Up to now, most AC studies of the dielectric properties have been performed under low field intensity conditions, i.e., in the linear regime $\sim V/mm$.⁹ In contrast, the high-field electrical properties in polymers are mainly reported under DC conditions.^{10,11} Potentially, some of the DC mechanisms (e.g., charge injection, bulk conduction, recombination, and space charge formation) can also occur under AC field stress, but it is still unclear how these processes contribute under dynamic conditions. Furthermore, additional electrical processes, unique to AC conditions, may also have a field dependency that is important to quantify.

Polyimides (PIs) are a broad class of materials used in a variety of diverse applications such as aerospace, power electronics, and microelectronics. They are widely used as coating films for electronic device surface passivation.¹² They are also employed in

wafer-level packaging processes¹³ and as the insulating barrier for digital isolators.¹⁴ Aromatic PI films are technologically important owing to their thermal stability (>500 °C), high glass transition temperature, low dielectric constant, mechanical toughness, chemical resistance, and planarizing properties.¹⁵ For decades, the dielectric and electrical properties of PI films have been largely investigated in low AC field^{16,17} or high DC field conditions.^{18–21} However, in common with most of the insulating polymers, their dielectric properties in intense AC electric fields are not well characterized.

For comparison, in ferroelectric materials, such as poly(vinylidene fluoride) (PVDF), the field delineating the transition from linear to nonlinear behavior is easily observed and relatively well understood.²² However, the threshold field, E_{th} , for more insulating media, such as insulating polymers, appears at higher values where its detection is not trivial. The experimental techniques available for observing the linear/nonlinear transition at very high fields and frequency have been limited. Current–voltage (I–V) measurements under high-voltage (HV) AC bias have been the preferred method to evaluate the field dependency of the dielectric properties in polymeric films.^{23–27} Nevertheless, this is typically over a limited frequency range, and close to the power line frequency 50/60 Hz. It is only recently, with the advent of broadband dielectric spectroscopy at high voltage, that new research avenues have been opened and used to understand the nonlinear dielectric properties and their underlying physics. The technique has been applied to liquids^{28,29} and ferroelectrics,³⁰ but until now, not to insulating materials, like polymer films.

This work describes the experimental measurement of the nonlinear dielectric threshold properties in PI films, from low to very high-intensity AC fields. It compares HV broadband dielectric spectroscopic results with standard I–V characterization using high DC voltages. The underlying DC contribution to the AC conductivity is discussed and other AC polarization features at high field and high frequency are discussed. Finally, it is shown that in the ohmic region, below E_{th} , the AC dielectric properties remain fully linear and have no dependencies on frequency.

II. EXPERIMENTAL PART

A. Materials and sample preparation

Polyimide under investigation was prepared from a polyamic acid solution (PAA), precursor of a pyromellitic dianhydride (PMDA) and an oxydianiline diamine (ODA) dissolved in an *N*-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP) polar solvent.

Figure 1 shows a cross-section sketch of the PI film test structure. The samples were prepared on an industrial production line inside a high-class clean-room facility. The PAA solution was spin-cast onto Si wafers (8 in.-diameter) possessing a top PECVD oxide layer that, in turn, supported a bottom electrode (blanket electroplated TiW/Au bilayer). The spin speed was adjusted to give a final PI film thickness of about 6 μm after curing at high temperatures. The uppermost surface of the deposited films was subsequently metallized with another electroplated TiW/Au bilayer. Photolithographic processing generated circular PI capacitors with concentric guarding rings. The test structures were finally encapsulated with a thicker, 15 μm , capping PI layer to suppress corona

discharges. Further details concerning the fabrication process can be found elsewhere.²¹

B. Measurements

Three techniques were used for the electrical characterization in this study: (i) I–V in DC, (ii) I–V in AC, and (iii) high-voltage broadband dielectric spectroscopy (HVBDS). Only the I–V in DC and HVBDS is detailed further and analyzed in the following. Before any electrical test, each sample was oven dried at 150 °C for 2 days. All the tests were performed at room temperature condition (23 °C).

The complex conductivity, $\sigma_{AC} = \sigma'_{AC} + i\sigma''_{AC}$, is defined as the ratio between the current density, j , and the harmonic driving electric field, E , as $j = \sigma_{AC}E$. It can also be written in terms of the complex relative permittivity, ϵ , as $\sigma_{AC} = i\omega\epsilon\epsilon_0$ where ω is the angular frequency and ϵ_0 is the permittivity of free space.

The DC conductivity (σ_X) was derived from measured I–V conduction currents under DC bias fields ($\omega = 0$). In this case, the sample was connected to a high-voltage DC source (6.5 kV) and the transient current was recorded using a Keithley electrometer. The guard ring was grounded to form a homogeneous field and to suppress any surface leakage current. Measurements involved stepping through a voltage sequence of 30 min of polarization (V_{on}), to reach the steady state current, followed by a 30 min, short-circuit (V_{off}), depolarization phase. The σ_X values were calculated from steady state currents as a function of the electric field (E).

The HVBDS measurement technique couples a Novocontrol spectrometer with a high-voltage HVB-4000 boost module (see Fig. 1). The total current i_2 and its phase φ_2 are measured through an I-to-V converter achieving a resolution down to 0.1 nA. The HV

FIG. 1. Cross-sectional sketch of the PI capacitor test structures used for HVBDS and I–V AC characterizations. The general measurement principles for each technique are also shown.

module could provide $\pm 2000 V_{\text{peak}}$ in a frequency range from 100 mHz to 10 kHz. Ignoring higher harmonics, the real dielectric permittivity (ϵ'), the dielectric loss factor ($\tan \delta$), and the alternating conductivity (σ_{AC}) were measured in voltage steps of $100 V_{\text{rms}}$ up to $1.4 kV_{\text{rms}}$ (see Fig. 2). Some frequency limitation at high voltage was experienced due to the sample capacitance. However, for each frequency, the measured voltage feedback on V_I was used to accurately calculate the electrical field, E , applied to the sample. The complex permittivity was measured by first filtering the higher harmonic content, and so only the fundamental component is treated here.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Nonlinear dielectric properties through HVBDs

Figure 3 presents the frequency dependence of the dielectric permittivity, loss factor, and AC conductivity of a PI film, for applied signals from low to high field. At electric fields below $70 V_{\text{rms}}/\mu\text{m}$, it is observed that all the dielectric properties (ϵ' , $\tan \delta$, and σ_{AC}) in the frequency range up to 100 Hz do not exhibit any field sensitivity. Thus, the permittivity value is relatively stable, around 3.2–3.25, the loss tangent varies slightly from 5×10^{-3} down to 3×10^{-3} , and the AC conductivity is proportional to frequency, fitting a power law with an exponent close to unity. This latter behavior, at low field, can be explained in terms of a linear dipolar orientation. It has been reported in PI, and other solid dielectrics, and is well-known as the Jonscher “universal” dielectric response. It is described by the following power law:^{17,31}

$$\sigma_{AC} = \omega \epsilon_0 \epsilon'' = \omega \epsilon_0 \epsilon' \tan \delta \propto \omega^{n_\sigma}, \quad (1)$$

FIG. 2. HVBDs frequency-modulated voltage sequence applied to the samples for linear and nonlinear dielectric properties characterization.

where ω is the angular frequency, ϵ_0 is the vacuum permittivity (8.854×10^{-12} F), and n_σ is a power-law exponent (ideally, $n_\sigma = 1$ for purely dipolar behavior).

On the contrary, at higher fields, above $70 V_{\text{rms}}/\mu\text{m}$, the dielectric properties start to be field-dependent. The loss factor, $\tan \delta$, and the AC conductivity, σ_{AC} , progressively increase with the applied field, the effect being larger at lower frequencies. Similar observations were reported for time-domain I–V measurements in both low-density polyethylene (LDPE) by Tokoro *et al.*²⁴ and silicon oxide (SiO_x) films by Le Sueur and Jonscher.³² They underline the significant impact of a high-magnitude dissipative current component on the high-field dielectric losses.

With an increase in field, the conductivity departs from an $n_\sigma = 1$ pure dipole power-law behavior and tends to $n_\sigma = 0$, corresponding to a pure hopping conduction process dominating the dielectric response. Meanwhile, a decrease is observed in the power-law exponent ($m_{\tan \delta}$) of the loss tangent as the applied electric field increases. The $m_{\tan \delta}$ factor departs from values close to zero, describing the low-field dipolar polarization and tends to reach $m_{\tan \delta} = -1$, corresponding to the case of a pure hopping conduction process.

Figure 4 plots the variation in the power-law exponents n_σ and $m_{\tan \delta}$ (fitted at low frequency between 0.1 and 1 Hz) as a function of the peak electric field. Both n_σ and $m_{\tan \delta}$ diverge from their quasi-ideal values, respectively, +1 and 0, at a field value around $100 V_{\text{peak}}/\mu\text{m}$ for very low frequency. Above $100 V_{\text{peak}}/\mu\text{m}$, both n_σ and $m_{\tan \delta}$ monotonically decrease albeit through an intermediate flattening observed at an electric field around $200 V_{\text{peak}}/\mu\text{m}$. Beyond this field, the power-law exponents continue to drop approaching a dielectric response corresponding to a pure conduction process. It is likely that this condition is finally reached at breakdown, as shown by the extrapolated dashed lines. However, during the experiment, n_σ and $m_{\tan \delta}$ remain far from the pure conduction ($n_\sigma = 0.32$ and $m_{\tan \delta} = -0.64$ at $345 V_{\text{peak}}/\mu\text{m}$). A conductive state is usually easily obtained when the charge carrier energy is driven by temperature.^{17,31} This implies that even if the pure DC conduction process is part of the dielectric losses, it cannot entirely explain the dielectric response in terms of nonlinearity.

B. Loss factor field and frequency dependencies

In this section, the loss factor is considered in more detail. In Fig. 5, the dielectric loss factor is replotted as a function of the electric field for various iso-frequencies. It shows that $\tan \delta$ remains field-independent up to a threshold field $E_{th} = E_{PF}$. The E_{PF} threshold field corresponds to the transition at which the Poole–Frenkel (PF) AC polarization becomes comparable with the background resistive contributions.^{24,33–36} With increasing frequency, $E_{PF}(\omega)$ shifts toward higher electric fields reaching around $180 V_{\text{peak}}/\mu\text{m}$ and is accompanied by a reduction in the magnitude of $\tan \delta$. This highlights the significance of Poole–Frenkel AC polarization even at higher frequencies.

The frequency dependence of the threshold field $E_{PF}(\omega)$ is plotted in Fig. 6 and it is compared to the DC threshold field, $E_X(\omega = 0) = 45 V_{\text{peak}}/\mu\text{m}$. This value is high, compared, for example, with fields required to initiate charge injection for a XLPE cable.

FIG. 3. Frequency dependency of the dielectric properties in PI films from low to high electric field: (a) permittivity ϵ' , (b) loss tangent $\tan \delta$, and (c) AC conductivity σ_{AC} . The $m_{\tan \delta} = -1$ and $n_{\sigma} = 0$ solid lines indicate the ideal power law for a pure DC conduction process in each representation.

However, thin films prepared in a clean-room environment, as used in this study, tend to exhibit superior properties. Over a large frequency range, $E_{PF}(\omega)$ increases from approximately $90 V_{\text{peak}}/\mu\text{m}$ at 0.1 Hz up to $180 V_{\text{peak}}/\mu\text{m}$ at 100 Hz, the last frequency where a value could be extracted. Given that $E_{PF}(\omega)$ is always greater than E_X implies that the underlying mechanism requires high field and/or high frequency to be activated.

The E_{PF} field transition for PI films is an indicator of the conditions required for reliable electrical behavior and can be used to safeguard its use in electronic applications. Consequently, below E_{PF} no electric aging mechanisms should occur and the PI lifetime can be considered “infinite” since, below E_{PF} , the loss factor $\tan \delta$ is fully linear and independent of the frequency.

To fully understand the underlying mechanisms controlling the dielectric losses in AC, it is important to detail the different potential contributions to the total loss factor. It has been shown by Tokoro *et al.*, in LDPE and in polypropylene (PP) films, that the

dielectric loss factor is field and frequency-dependent and can be expressed as^{24,33–36}

$$\tan \delta(E, \omega) = \tan \delta_0 + \Delta \tan \delta(E, \omega), \quad (2)$$

where $\tan \delta_0$ is the low-field, frequency-independent loss factor and $\Delta \tan \delta$ is the field-dependent dielectric loss component given by

$$\Delta \tan \delta(E, \omega) = \tan \delta_{PF}(E, \omega) + \frac{\sigma_X(E)}{\omega \epsilon_0 \epsilon'}, \quad (3)$$

with $\tan \delta_{PF}$ being the field- and frequency-dependent Poole-Frenkel AC polarization loss component and σ_X being the nonlinear field-dependent DC conductivity.

The total $\tan \delta$ is made up of various components such as the low-field loss factor ($\tan \delta_0$) due to the local dipolar orientation, the interfacial polarization due to macroscopic charge transport

FIG. 4. Field dependency of the $m_{\tan \delta}$ and n_{σ} power-law exponents fitted from 0.1 to 1 Hz. The asymptotic $m_{\tan \delta} = -1$ and $n_{\sigma} = 0$ solid lines indicate a pure DC conduction process. The dashed lines are extrapolations from high field toward breakdown. Vertical up-arrows indicate the transition to nonlinear behavior at low frequency.

and trapping in bulk, and the conduction component of the loss factor ($\sigma_X / \omega \epsilon_0 \epsilon'$) due to the carrier transport process. When the carrier transport process is considered, not only the DC leakage current but also the carrier generation and transport process inherent in AC field ($\tan \delta_{PF}$) can be part of the overall dielectric loss response. The field dependency of $\tan \delta$ can be affected by the Poole-Frenkel emission of electrons coming from the donor-like states in the bulk. In such a case, $\tan \delta$ can increase significantly

FIG. 5. Loss factor, $\tan \delta$, as a function of the peak electric field for various frequencies.

FIG. 6. Poole-Frenkel polarization electric field threshold, E_{PF} [extracted from $\tan \delta(E)$] vs the driving frequency for PI films. The solid line corresponds to the DC threshold field, E_X , measured by I-V.

due to the enhanced number of carriers (i.e., $\tan \delta_{PF}$ and/or $\sigma_X / \omega \epsilon_0 \epsilon'$) depending on field and frequency conditions.

C. High-field nonlinear conductivity in AC

To quantitatively assess the weight of each of the $\tan \delta$ components, one has to analyze the results in terms of high-field nonlinear conductivity. To do so, the general AC conductivity Eq. (1) (i.e., the Jonscher’s “universal” power law^{31,37}) is combined with Eqs. (2) and (3) such that the total dielectric loss $\tan \delta$ can be rewritten as a total AC conductivity,³⁶

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{AC}(E, \omega) &= \omega \epsilon_0 \epsilon' \tan \delta(E, \omega) \\ &= \omega \epsilon_0 \epsilon' (\tan \delta_0 + \tan \delta_{PF}(E, \omega)) + \sigma_X(E) \\ &= \sigma_0(\omega) + \sigma_{PF}(E, \omega) + \sigma_X(E), \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where σ_{PF} is the field and frequency-dependent AC conductivity component related to the Poole-Frenkel polarization process (i.e., carrier generation and transport) coming from donor centers in the bulk.

Figure 7 presents the AC and DC conductivity variation (respectively, σ_{AC} and σ_X) as a function of the peak electric field and for different frequencies in PI films. One can observe that σ_{AC} is much larger than σ_X for $E < 200 \text{ V}_{\text{peak}}/\mu\text{m}$. However, at higher fields, the difference narrows under the influence of the increasing nonlinearity. Even though for the lowest frequencies (lower than 10 Hz), a high-field convergence of both AC and DC conductivities is observed, for higher frequencies, σ_{AC} remains significantly larger than σ_X . Such a difference emphasizes that the high-field and high-frequency behavior of σ_{AC} is mainly controlled by an additional AC conduction process.

The AC conductivity (σ_{AC}), defined by Eq. (4), corresponds to the sum of the low-field dipolar conductivity σ_0 , the Poole–Frenkel emission of intrinsic charge carriers from the bulk (σ_{PF}), and the DC conduction coming from both bulk charge transport and injection process from electrodes (σ_X). The σ_{PF} contribution is a pure feature of AC and depends on field and frequency conditions. Thus, the Poole–Frenkel effect is evident in Fig. 7 and is of a larger magnitude than the DC conduction process. This is particularly true with a combination of high frequency and an applied field more than E_X for which σ_{PF} is a stronger function of E . On the contrary, below E_X , the σ_{PF} component vanishes compared to σ_X for the entire frequency range. Consequently, these results confirm that E_X corresponds to a conservative threshold below which all the conduction processes (both DC and AC) are negligible and will not induce electrical damage capable of affecting the insulation reliability of PI films.

D. Poole–Frenkel conduction modeling in high frequency

Usually, in a high DC field, most of the charge carriers are injected electrons and holes coming from the interfaces with electrodes. The carriers are captured in traps to form a homo space charge. Under an AC field, the charge carriers that increase the loss factor can be electronic or ionic in origin. These charges come from intrinsic donor centers within the bulk. The influence of the injected charges at the electrodes in AC is very limited because of the fast polarity changes. As a result, the AC injection has always been considered a small contribution to the dielectric loss. Based on the results presented here, this is partly correct, up to an intermediate

FIG. 7. AC conductivity vs peak electric field in PI films for various frequencies from DC up to 10 kHz. The σ_X , σ_{PF} , and σ_0 conductivity components correspond to the field-dependent pure DC conduction, the field and frequency-dependent Poole–Frenkel charge polarization in AC, and the field-independent capacitive current contributions, respectively. Notice the nonlinear response can only be observed when it surpasses the linear contribution, $\sigma_0(\omega)$.

field. However, at very high fields, charge injection in AC must be considered a significant part of the dielectric loss. For the rest, the Poole–Frenkel effect in AC field is responsible for the larger part of the AC conductivity and dielectric loss assuming, $E > E_X$. Jonscher³⁸ and Jonscher and Loh³⁹ introduced such an AC conduction process by modifying the classical Poole–Frenkel law to describe the charge generation in volume in an alternating field regime.

For decades, it has been assumed that a small-amplitude AC field causes a higher current, due to hopping conduction, compared to the corresponding DC field (as shown in Fig. 7).³¹ However, the additional effect of a large-amplitude AC field, of the order of magnitude of the DC field, will depend on frequency. At low frequency, the instantaneous energy that charge carriers gain always remains in equilibrium with the steady state. At high frequency, the carrier energy can no longer follow the magnitude of the instantaneous field. Therefore, the energy gain is cumulative and the amplitude of oscillation increases as does the energy and hence the mobility as illustrated in Fig. 8.

Consequently, when the AC field is high enough to cause sufficient potential well barrier lowering, the carrier can be thermal excited and overcome the barrier. At a sufficiently high frequency, the charge carrier will be able to describe a ratchet-like trajectory, progressively distancing itself from the donor center. This process has been called the “jacking-up” effect by Jonscher.^{33,38} Once the charge carriers have gained enough energy to reach the conduction band, they become free to move in the high field, away from the donor. The combined high-intensity, high-frequency field enhances the probability of charge carrier emission and so increases the free charge density contributing to the AC conduction.

FIG. 8. Conduction processes comparison between hopping in DC and Poole–Frenkel frequency-assisted detrapping in AC high electric fields on a carrier trapped in a Coulombic potential well of a donor center. A sufficiently high-frequency AC field produces an alternating movement of the carrier, namely, the *jacking-up effect*, that leads to a high effective temperature within the center and to an enhanced probability of emission in the conduction band compared to under DC field.

The Poole–Frenkel plot of the AC current density j vs $E^{0.5}$ for various frequencies is presented in Fig. 9.

From the high-field region, above E_{PF} , the experimental data were fitted using the modified Poole–Frenkel equation which is given by^{39,40}

$$j = j_0 \exp\left[-\left(W_0 - \gamma\sqrt{E}\right)/kT\right], \quad (5)$$

where j_0 is the pre-exponential current at infinite temperature, W_0 is the average potential well depth at $E = 0$, $\gamma\sqrt{E}$ is the potential barrier lowering quantity with $\gamma = (e^3/\pi\epsilon_0\epsilon_r)^{1/2}$,⁴¹ e is the elementary charge, k is Boltzmann’s constant, T is the temperature, and ϵ_r is the optical relative permittivity compared to that of free space, ϵ_0 . On a Poole–Frenkel plot, therefore, the slope, $\left(\frac{dj}{dE^{0.5}}\right)$, yields the ratio γ/T as

$$\text{slope} = e\beta/kT = \gamma/kT. \quad (6)$$

Assuming a calculated value for γ , an effective temperature, T_c , can be extracted for carriers at a given frequency. The effective temperature is a function of the lattice temperature T_0 and of the frequency such that $T_c(\omega) > T_0$.³⁸

Alternatively, an effective γ_{eff} can be derived from the AC slopes of the PF conduction process, assuming a constant experimental temperature. The result of this calculation is plotted in Fig. 10 as a function of the driving electric field frequency.

One can observe that γ_{eff} is decreasing with increasing frequency. This highlights a more probable de-trapping process for charge carriers from donor sites when it is assisted by the frequency of the electric field, as described by the *jacking-up* effect. It is noted that the γ values obtained both from the high-field DC conduction slope and from calculation using the relative permittivity of these PI

films ($\epsilon_r = 3.25$) are close to each other and are higher than γ_{eff} obtained under AC. This confirms that the AC Poole–Frenkel polarization enables the generation and transport of extra charge carriers coming from deep traps into the conduction band that would not escape otherwise at DC.

In the alternative interpretation, Fig. 11 presents the frequency dependence of the effective temperature T_c obtained from the AC slopes in the PF region for the PI films. It also reports the T_c calculated for the DC regime (331 K) and the lattice temperature T_0 of the sample (298 K). Under DC conditions, the effective temperature $T_c(\omega = 0)$ remains close to T_0 . On the contrary, in AC conditions there is a significant and progressive rise of $T_c(\omega)$ with increasing frequency. This corresponds to an enhancement of the localized temperature at the carrier level assisted by frequency. This interpretation was first suggested by Jonscher *et al.* who observed that excitation with high-frequency AC fields was equivalent to DC conditions at higher temperature.^{38,39,41} Consequently, such a high effective temperature T_c , induced by high frequency, increases the probability of trapped carriers gaining sufficient energy to be released into the conduction band.

It is also worth noting, from Eq. (5), that the current density becomes independent of frequency at a saturation field E_c at which $\gamma\sqrt{E_c} = W_0$. Consequently, by using a saturation field $E_c \sim 500 \text{ V}_{rms}/\mu\text{m}$, obtained from the PF model extrapolation for the different frequencies (see Fig. 9) and using the γ_{DC} value extracted from the DC measurement gives a reasonable average potential well depth $W_0 \sim 0.85 \text{ eV}$ for these PI films.

In summary, the AC conduction in PI films under combined high field and high frequency obeys a Poole–Frenkel charge emission process. Such a mechanism occurs by the means of a *jacking-up* effect that reemits more easily in AC some of the

FIG. 9. Poole–Frenkel plot of the AC current density vs $E^{0.5}$ for PI films at various frequencies from DC up to 6.66 kHz. The dashed lines show the fits in the identified Poole–Frenkel field range above E_{PF} . A crossover field $E_c \sim 500 \text{ V}_{rms}/\mu\text{m}$ is obtained from the PF model extrapolation.

FIG. 10. Frequency dependence of the effective γ_{eff} of the Poole–Frenkel process calculated from high-field AC conduction slopes. The horizontal solid lines correspond to γ obtained from the high-field DC conduction slope and from calculation using the relative permittivity of these PI films ($\epsilon_r = 3.25$). The calculation implicitly assumes a high density of acceptor sites, which is unlikely to be strictly satisfied.

trapped charges from the PI bulk (usually trapped in DC) into the conduction band and this mechanism is strongly assisted by the frequency dependency of the carrier effective temperature $T_c(\omega)$. This effect appears as the most likely to describe the AC additional nonlinear contribution to the high-field conductivity and dielectric loss factor. However, this Poole–Frenkel AC process becomes insignificant whatever the frequency on the condition that the electric field magnitude is maintained below E_{PF} , or, more conservatively, below the DC threshold field E_X (i.e., at the earliest appearance of the conduction nonlinearity).

E. Power loss dissipation and E-field/frequency design rules for applications

The measured data of Fig. 3 have been represented as 3D surface plots in Fig. 12. They show a clear distinction between a linear regime, where the complex permittivity is independent of field and frequency, and a nonlinear regime for which the properties are a function of both parameters. In this region, with log–log axes, contours form straight lines, indicating that the dielectric properties depend on the product of field and frequency.

The Poole–Frenkel analysis is confined to the variations of conductive loss only. A suitable expression that captures the behavior of both the real and imaginary variation of the dielectric response with respect to the applied electric field (in rms) E , at frequency f , is introduced here as

$$\frac{\epsilon^*}{\epsilon_\infty} = 1 - i\Delta + \left[i^{-\alpha} \left(\frac{E}{E_0} \right)^{\alpha m \cos\theta} \left(\frac{f}{f_0} \right)^{\alpha m \sin\theta} \right], \quad (7)$$

where E_0 and f_0 are characteristic field and frequency, respectively, and Δ , α , and m are constant parameters.

FIG. 11. Frequency dependence of the effective temperature T_c calculated from the AC $j(E^{0.5})$ slopes in the PF region for PI films. The solid lines show the calculated T_c for the DC regime (331 K) and the lattice temperature of the sample T_0 (298 K).

The expression describes the complex permittivity ϵ^* , normalized to its high-frequency value ϵ_∞ . It is comprised of a linear ($1 - i\Delta$) and a nonlinear component shown in parentheses. For simplicity, the linear response is treated as non-dispersive with $\Delta = 0.00345$. The power-law exponents are first determined by the angle θ , that is, the angle that the parallel contours of Fig. 12 make with the logarithmic frequency axis, extracted here as $\sim -5^\circ$; the negative value indicates an inverse power relationship for

FIG. 12. 3D surface plot of field and frequency dependency of the dielectric properties in PI films: (a) real part of the permittivity ϵ' and (b) loss tangent $\tan \delta$. Contours, which have been projected onto a plane surface, form parallel lines in the highly nonlinear region corresponding to high field and low frequency.

FIG. 13. The complex modulus parameterized by frequency values as shown in the legend. The solid line shows the fit according to Eq. (7). The E-field increases along the “semi-circle” from right to left.

frequency. The nonlinear contribution is also governed by a characteristic field, E_0 , and frequency, f_0 , combination, here $281 \text{ V}/\mu\text{m}$ and 0.2 Hz , respectively. Such pairs are not unique but correspond to coordinates at which the real and imaginary parts of the permittivity are equal and, thus, are straightforward to extract. The quantity $E_0 f_0^{-\tan\theta}$ is, however, invariant. The parameter α makes the loss tangent tends to $\tan(\alpha\pi/2)$ in the high-field limit, corresponding to constant phase behavior. To estimate α , the modulus ($1/\epsilon^*$) is plotted on the complex plane as a “Cole-Cole” plot, as shown in Fig. 13. The value of α is then approximated as the ratio of imaginary and real modulus at the point of maximum imaginary modulus. This procedure yields $\alpha \sim 0.92$. The final element, the

FIG. 14. A comparison between measured (symbols) and fitted data (solid lines) of the imaginary part of the permittivity (ϵ'') according to Eq. (7).

FIG. 15. The dissipated power density with rms electric field E , and frequency f , plotted on a log–log scale. The dashed line indicates the threshold contour E_{eq} , as given by Eq. (8). The response is highly nonlinear for fields and frequencies to the right of this line. The dot-dashed line indicates the contour at which the nonlinear component of loss equals that of the linear contribution with $10^{-3}\Delta$.

exponent m , is found from the slope of a $\log(E)$, $\log(\epsilon'')$ plot (not shown here) giving $m \sim 7.8$. Without further optimization, these values have been used in the fit plotted in Fig. 14. This shows the imaginary part of the permittivity varying with frequency, parameterized by the applied bias voltage and indicates the nonlinear lossy response has indeed been captured by Eq. (7).

It is important to distinguish the conditions under which the material response is either linear or nonlinear. Using Eq. (7), an expression for a frequency-dependent threshold field E_{eq} is proposed here that corresponds to the condition that the nonlinear loss contribution is equal to that of the linear contribution, namely,

$$E_{eq} = E_0 \left(\frac{f}{f_0}\right)^{-\tan\theta} \left[\frac{\Delta}{\sin\left(\frac{\alpha\pi}{2}\right)} \right]^{\frac{1}{\alpha m \cos\theta}} \quad (8)$$

The dielectric power loss density P_d is plotted in Fig. 15 based on Eq. (9),⁴²

$$P_d = \omega\epsilon_0\epsilon''E^2. \quad (9)$$

The measured region is divided between a linear and nonlinear response by the dashed contour corresponding to Eq. (8). To the “left” of this line, the power dissipation increases with both applied field and frequency, as expected. In contrast, in the nonlinear region, the dependence on frequency is much reduced and the applied field is the dominant parameter. For many applications, linearity is of utmost importance and is a key criterion for a long

term, reliable HV insulating performance. This implies that in high-voltage service conditions at 60 Hz, as well as at least up to 10 kHz, the electric field applied on PI film should not exceed $E_{th} \approx 100 V_{rms}/\mu m$ throughout the entire insulated device (both uniform and fringe fields) to get the benefit of the highest reliability.

IV. CONCLUSION

This work carried out an experimental examination of the nonlinear dielectric properties of PI films in the AC regime at both high field and high frequency. The results show, first, that the nonlinear DC conduction is a significant component in the high-field AC response and influences both the dielectric loss and AC conductivity. Second, for combined high field and high frequency, an additional nonlinearity is induced, specific to AC excitation. This extra contribution is attributed to the AC Poole-Frenkel polarization process at high fields. It is associated with increased charge carrier de-trapping that is exacerbated by high frequency (namely, the *jacking-up* effect). Similar evidence was reported in oxide layers. In the present study, it is shown that the dielectric properties of PI films remain fully linear and frequency-independent for electric fields below a threshold E_{PF} . A novel suitable expression that describes the large signal response of the complex permittivity $\epsilon^*(E, \omega)$ is proposed here with the Cole-Cole format. A subsequent equation for a frequency-dependent threshold field $E_{th}(E, \omega)$ has also been presented defined by the equality of linear and nonlinear loss. Finally, from data modeling, it is shown that the dielectric properties and power dissipation density in PI films are fully linear and frequency-independent up to an AC electric field $E = E_{PF} \approx E_{th} \approx 100 V_{rms}/\mu m$ and more conservatively below a threshold field $E_X \sim 45 V/\mu m$ (i.e., the end of the ohmic region). Based on the high-voltage dielectric spectroscopy analysis applied to PI films, this study highlights that polyimide-based insulated electronic devices that are designed to continuously operate below this threshold field (including both uniform and fringe fields) will remain immune to a frequency-dependent electrical aging. Their lifetime should not be affected in any way.

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AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

Conflict of Interest

The authors have no conflicts to disclose.

Author Contributions

Sombel Diahm: Conceptualization (lead); Data curation (lead); Formal analysis (lead); Funding acquisition (equal); Investigation (equal); Methodology (equal); Project administration (equal);

Resources (equal); Software (supporting); Supervision (lead); Validation (equal); Visualization (equal); Writing – original draft (lead); Writing – review & editing (equal). **Paul Lambkin:** Data curation (equal); Formal analysis (equal); Investigation (equal); Methodology (equal); Software (lead); Validation (equal); Visualization (equal); Writing – review & editing (lead). **Baoxing Chen:** Conceptualization (supporting); Funding acquisition (equal); Resources (equal); Supervision (equal); Validation (equal); Visualization (equal); Writing – review & editing (supporting).

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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